

Supplementary materials of

Computational investigation for exploring botanical ingredients as potential negative allosteric modulators targeting metabotropic glutamate receptor 5

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Fig. S1. Crystallographic structure of mGluR5 protein co-crystallized with M-MPEP (colored in magenta). mGluR5, Metabotropic glutamate receptor 5; M-MPEP, 2-[2-(3-methoxyphenyl)ethynyl]-6-methyl-pyridine.

Fig. S2. Best binding poses of natural hits (A) 3'-HPS, (B) gigantol, (C) isorhapontigenin, and (D) coclaurine, respectively, superimposed on the co-crystal (colored in white) at the active pocket of mGluR5. 3'-HPS, 3'-Hydroxypterostilbene; mGluR5, metabotropic glutamate receptor 5.

Fig. S3. Number of interactions formed during the molecular dynamics simulations of (A) 3'-HPS, (B) gigantol, (C) isorhapontigenin, (D) coclaurine, (E) M-MPEP, and (F) MPEP. Hydrogen bonding, π - π stacking, and π -cation interactions were colored in navy blue, red, and green, respectively. 3'-HPS, 3'-Hydroxypterostilbene; M-MPEP, 2-[2-(3-methoxyphenyl)ethynyl]-6-methyl-pyridine; MPEP, 2-methyl-6-phenylethynyl-pyridine.

Fig. S4. Post-dynamics interaction analysis clustered in the last 10 ns trajectories frames of (A) 3'-HPS, (B) gigantol, (C) isorhapontigenin, (D) coclaurine, (E) M-MPEP, and (F) MPEP, respectively, against mGluR5. 3'-HPS, 3'-Hydroxypterostilbene; MPEP, 2-methyl-6-phenylethynyl-pyridine; M-MPEP, 2-[2-(3-methoxyphenyl)ethynyl]-6-methyl-pyridine; mGluR5, metabotropic glutamate receptor 5.

Table S1. Molecular binding interactions of best hits against the mGluR5 protein.

Serial No.	Natural hits	Hydrogen bonding	Hydrophobic
1	3'-HPS	Ser654 (-23.07 kcal/mol), Ser658 (-33.40 kcal/mol)	Ile651 (-28.55 kcal/mol), Leu904 (-35.15 kcal/mol), Trp945 (-52.88 kcal/mol), Phe948 (-38.47 kcal/mol), Pro655 (-15.23 kcal/mol), Trp659 (-48.38 kcal/mol), Val966 (-35.48 kcal/mol)
2	Gigantol	Gly624 (-39.55 kcal/mol), Ser654 (-20.19 kcal/mol), Ser658 (-30.97 kcal/mol), Ser969 (-31.27 kcal/mol)	Ile651 (-27.46 kcal/mol), Leu904 (-34.01 kcal/mol), Trp945 (-45.69 kcal/mol), Phe948 (-36.33 kcal/mol), Pro655 (-10.69 kcal/mol), Trp659 (-47.30 kcal/mol), Met962 (-40.99 kcal/mol), Val966 (-32.02 kcal/mol)
3	Isorhapontigenin	Gly624 (-39.55 kcal/mol), Ser658 (-30.97 kcal/mol)	Ile651 (-27.46 kcal/mol), Leu904 (-34.01 kcal/mol), Trp945 (-45.69 kcal/mol), Phe948 (-36.33 kcal/mol), Pro655 (-10.69 kcal/mol), Trp659 (-47.30 kcal/mol), Val966 (-32.02 kcal/mol), Ala970 (-39.32 kcal/mol)
4	Coclaurine	Ser654 (-20.04 kcal/mol), Ser658 (-31.41 kcal/mol), Val966 (-33.28 kcal/mol)	Ile651 (-27.81 kcal/mol), Pro655 (-14.15 kcal/mol), Tyr659 (-48.97 kcal/mol), Leu904 (-33.99 kcal/mol), Trp945 (-48.86 kcal/mol), Phe948 (-35.81 kcal/mol), Met962 (-39.37 kcal/mol)
5	M-MPEP	Gly624 (-39.55 kcal/mol), Ser658 (-30.97 kcal/mol), Ser969 (-31.27 kcal/mol)	Ile651 (-27.46 kcal/mol), Pro655 (-10.69 kcal/mol), Tyr659 (-47.30 kcal/mol), Leu904 (-34.01 kcal/mol), Trp945 (-45.69 kcal/mol), Phe948 (-36.33 kcal/mol), Val966 (-32.02 kcal/mol), Ala973 (-37.14 kcal/mol)
6	MPEP	Ile625 (-34.51 kcal/mol), Ser658 (-31.24 kcal/mol), Ser969 (-33.69 kcal/mol)	Ile651 (-24.86 kcal/mol), Pro655 (-13.82 kcal/mol), Tyr659 (-49.72 kcal/mol), Leu904 (-34.56 kcal/mol), Trp945 (-48.44 kcal/mol), Phe948 (-35.90 kcal/mol), Val966 (-32.49 kcal/mol), Ala973 (-37.72 kcal/mol)

3'-HPS, 3'-Hydroxypterostilbene; MPEP, 2-methyl-6-phenylethynyl-pyridine; M-MPEP, 2-[2-(3-methoxyphenyl)ethynyl]-6-methyl-pyridine; mGluR5, metabotropic glutamate receptor 5.

Table S2. Physicochemical properties and ADMET assessment of best natural hits. The predicted toxicity probability values were scaled between 0 (lower) and 1 (higher). Values with red color demonstrate a higher probability of predicted toxicity scores.

Serial No.	Parameters	3'-HPS	Gigantol	Isorhapontigenin	Coclaurine	M-MPEP	MPEP
1.	Mol Wt.	272.1	274.12	258.09	285.14	223.1	193.09
2.	HBD	2.0	2.0	3.0	3.0	0	0
3.	HBA	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	2	1
4.	Rot. bonds	4.0	5.0	3.0	3.0	1	0
5.	TPSA	58.92	58.92	69.92	61.72	22.12	12.89
6.	Solubility	-4.029	-3.774	-3.529	-2.591	-3.76	-3.889
7.	LogP _{o/w}	3.686	3.032	2.901	0.964	3.317	3.384
8.	SA score	2.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	2.0
9.	Caco-2	-5.136	-4.873	-4.927	-5.119	-4.73	-4.396
10.	BBB	0.01	0.075	0.005	0.097	0.032	0.466
11.	PPB (%)	84.143	90.482	86.926	66.714	98.3	98.8
12.	CL (mL/min/kg)	16.186	9.812	8.102	6.705	6.737	5.497
13.	Half-life (h)	1.286	1.39	1.563	1.77	0.496	0.537
14.	Oral toxicity	0.275	0.13	0.341	0.944	0.463	0.434
15.	Cardiotoxicity	0.381	0.502	0.209	0.531	0.236	0.195
16.	DILI	0.558	0.162	0.117	0.064	0.499	0.191
17.	Carcinogenicity	0.537	0.342	0.491	0.041	0.615	0.371
18.	Eye irritation	0.969	0.961	0.995	0.805	0.992	0.996
19.	Mutagenicity	0.739	0.561	0.646	0.452	0.68	0.593
20.	Hepatotoxicity	0.644	0.589	0.619	0.836	0.688	0.725
21.	Nephrotoxicity	0.298	0.393	0.131	0.384	0.253	0.142
22.	Hematotoxicity	0.115	0.233	0.062	0.019	0.14	0.093
23.	Genotoxicity	0.442	0.135	0.86	0.963	0.019	0.012
24.	Neurotoxicity	0.298	0.4	0.333	0.955	0.521	0.467

Mol Wt, Molecular weight; HBD, hydrogen bond donor; HBA, hydrogen bond acceptor; Rot, rotatable; TPSA, total polar surface area; SA, synthetic accessibility score; Caco-2, cancer coli-2; BBB, blood-brain barrier; PPB, plasma-protein binding; CL, clearance; DILI, drug-induced liver injury; ADMET, absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity.